

Carbon nanotubes magnetic hybrid nanocomposites for a rapid and selective preconcentration and clean-up of mercury species in water samples

Ana I. Corps Ricardo^a

Armando Sánchez-Cachero^a

María Jiménez-Moreno^a

Francisco J. Guzmán Bernardo^a

Rosa C. Rodríguez Martín-Doimeadios^{a, *}

Ángel Ríos^b

^aEnvironmental Sciences Institute (ICAM), Department of Analytical Chemistry and Food Technology, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Avda. Carlos III s/n, 45071 Toledo, Spain.

^b Department of Analytical Chemistry and Food Technology, Faculty of Chemical Sciences and Technologies, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Avda. Camilo José Cela s/n, 13071 Ciudad Real, Spain.

* Corresponding author:

Rosa Carmen Rodríguez Martín-Doimeadios

Environmental Sciences Institute (ICAM)

University of Castilla-La Mancha

E-45071 Toledo, Spain;

Telf: (+34) 925 268 800 Ext. 5420

Fax: (+34) 925 268 840

RosaCarmen.Rodriguez@uclm.es

Abstract

Hybrid nanocomposites based on Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) coated with different types of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been studied for the first time as sorbent materials for magnetic solid phase extraction (MSPE) for mercury speciation analysis. Monomethylmercury (MMHg) was the target mercury species in water samples and the adsorption and desorption processes were optimized based on this species. Single-walled CNT-MNP showed higher adsorption capacity than double-walled or multi-walled CNTs. Then, the magnetic sorbent was retrieved with an external magnet and MMHg was selectively desorbed from it with dichloromethane (DCM) in two steps with vortex agitation. Inorganic mercury was removed during the desorption stage. The rapid adsorption and desorption equilibrium, the magnetic separation of the sorbent, and the simple and fast synthesis of CNT-MNPs without any additional modification of the CNTs simplified and shortened the extraction procedure. The extract was submitted to derivatization of the mercury species by ethylation (with an optional nitrogen stream evaporation of the organic phase) and injection into a gas chromatograph coupled to an atomic fluorescence detector (GC-pyro-AFS). The overall procedure provides the preconcentration of MMHg up to 150 times and the removal of inorganic mercury at the same time. The procedural limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were 5.4 and 17.9 pg mL⁻¹, respectively. Moreover, magnetic nanocomposites can be reused at least 7 times without losing their efficiency. The methodology was validated in tap, dam and river water samples to evaluate the performance under real conditions with recoveries from 86 to 97% of spiked MMHg.

Keywords: magnetic solid phase extraction; carbon nanotubes; monomethylmercury; mercury speciation; water samples

1. Introduction

Mercury is one of the most toxic elements and has a severe impact on the environment and human health [1]. The toxicity and availability of mercury are defined by the chemical form (species) in which it is found. Thus, organic species, namely monomethylmercury (MMHg) or dimethylmercury (DMHg), are more toxic than inorganic species [2]. Monomethylmercury has a high capacity of bioaccumulation, bioconcentration and biomagnification in the aquatic environment [3]. Therefore, the environmental risk assessment of mercury involves necessarily to carry out speciation analysis in water samples with special emphasis on MMHg.

A large number of analytical techniques has been proposed for the detection and quantification of mercury species but the chromatographic separation hyphenated to atomic fluorescence spectroscopy (AFS) or inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) are the most widely used [4]. Among them, the separation by gas chromatography (GC) coupled to AFS via thermal pyrolysis (GC-pyro-AFS) is particularly advantageous in terms of sensitivity, selectivity and simplicity [5]. In spite of the significant developments in the analytical techniques, the mercury speciation analysis in water samples is still challenging. In these samples, the mercury species are found at ultra-trace levels and the concentration of MMHg is much lower than that of inorganic mercury. Indeed, the proportion of organic mercury in marine waters is typically less than 5% of the total mercury concentration [6,7]. Therefore, preconcentration and/or clean-up steps are necessary to detect such low concentrations of MMHg in water samples regardless to the selected techniques used for separation and detection.

Purge and trap, distillation and other techniques have been traditionally used to preconcentrate mercury species, but they are time consuming and involve tedious processes [8,9]. Other preconcentration techniques like dispersive liquid-liquid micro-extraction (DLLME), cloud point extraction (CPE) and solid phase (micro-) extraction (SPE, SPME) have emerged as valuable alternatives [4]. Among them, SPE is a very interesting option because it is simple, provides high enrichment factors, requires little volume of organic solvent and, contrary to other traditional techniques, it has experienced a significant evolution in the last years thanks to the use of nanomaterials (NMs) [8,10]. Carbon-based materials and, particularly, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are one of the most interesting options as sorbent material in SPE due to its structural, physical and chemical properties and also to their wide range of applications [11–13]. They have been widely used for the preconcentration of organic pollutants and heavy metals but in the field of trace element speciation the literature is still scarce [14]. In the

case of mercury, most studies have focused on the removal of inorganic mercury from waters [15-17], but few studies have been devoted up to now to mercury speciation analysis [18, 19]. Thus, as far as we know, there is only one paper reporting the use of CNTs for mercury species preconcentration [19]. In this work, CNTs were successfully used as sorbents in a continuous on-column preconcentration system after the derivatization of mercury species with sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDC). However, when the column dynamic extraction mode is used, the time limiting step is the large volume of sample to load to the cartridge. The alternative to the column mode would be the static batch mode but it is very difficult to separate the CNTs from aqueous solutions because of their little size [20]. To overcome these problems, a very interesting option is the new SPE mode based on the use of magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) which is known as magnetic solid-phase extraction (MSPE) [21]. The extraction efficiency and time are greatly improved because the MNPs can be well dispersed into the samples by ultrasonication or vortex agitation, and then shortly isolated from sample solutions by the application of an external magnetic field. Magnetic-SPE has been previously used for mercury speciation analysis [14, 22, 23] but, to our best knowledge, the hybrid nanocomposite made up of MNPs and CNTs has never been used for this purpose in spite of the unique properties of CNTs as sorbents and the operational advantages of MSPE.

The aim of this work has been to develop and validate an analytical method for mercury speciation analysis in water using CNT-MNPs. The proposed analytical strategy is based on the simultaneous preconcentration of MMHg and clean-up of inorganic mercury. This preconcentration/clean-up procedure along with the analysis by GC-pyro-AFS meets the requirements of selectivity and sensitivity for the determination of mercury species in water samples.

2. Experimental

2.1 Chemicals and materials

Stock standard solutions of $1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Hg^{2+} and MMHg were prepared by dissolving mercury (II) chloride (Panreac, Barcelona, Spain) in 5% HNO_3 (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and monomethylmercury chloride (Strem Chemicals, Newburyport, USA) in methanol. All stock solutions were stored in amber glass bottles at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Working standards were prepared daily by proper dilution with ultrapure water.

Sodium tetraethylborate (NaBEt_4) and sodium thiosulfate were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany) and Panreac (Barcelona, Spain), respectively. Sodium acetate trihydrate and glacial acetic acid (Scharlab, Barcelona, Spain) were used to prepare the buffer (0.1 M, pH 3.9). Hydrochloric acid (37%) was purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Alemania). Hexane, dichloromethane (DCM), isooctane and, acetonitrile (MeCN) were purchased from Scharlab (Barcelona, Spain). All chemicals were of analytical-reagent grade.

Iron (III) chloride hexahydrate, sodium acetate (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) and ethylene glycol (Panreac, Barcelona, Spain) were used to synthesize the magnetic nanoparticles. Different types of CNTs were studied in this work. The main characteristics and manufacturers of these nanocomposites are summarized in Table 1.

Ultrapure water ($18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}$ at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) was obtained from an Elga Purelab Ultra Analytic water purification system.

Helium C-50 was used as carrier gas, Argon C-50 was used as make-up at the transfer line and sheath gas at the AFS detector, and Nitrogen C-50 was used for preconcentration. All gases were from Carbueros Metálicos (Barcelona, Spain).

2.2 Instrumentation

The mercury species were separated and detected in a GC (Shimadzu GC-2010) coupled to an AFS detector (Millenium Merlin 10025 P.S. Analytical, United Kingdom) via a pyrolysis unit. The optimized conditions of the hyphenated system has already been described in the literature [24].

A conductivity meter (Crison, microCM 2200) and a pH-meter (Crison, Basic 20) were respectively used for the characterization of real water samples. A ZX3 vortex stirrer (Velp Scientifica, Usmate, Italy) was used in the extraction procedure.

A heating module (Reacti-Therm; Pierce, Rockford, IL, USA) with an evaporating unit was used for preconcentration.

2.3 Synthesis of CNT-MNPs

The multiwalled (MW), single walled (SW #1 and #2) or double walled (DW) CNT magnetic composites were prepared according to a previously described procedure [25, 26]. Briefly, this synthesis involves the addition of 0.014 g of $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.004 g of either MW, SW or DW-CNTs. This mixture was suspended in 0.75 mL ethylene glycol in a glass vial. Then, 0.036 g of sodium acetate was added and dissolved. The solution was allowed to stand at room temperature for 30 min. Afterwards, the glass vial was heated in an oven at 200 °C for 24 h. After cooling, the synthetic product was washed for 5 times with 1 mL of deionized water and the CNT-MNPs were recovered by applying a magnetic field via a magnet placed on the outer wall of the glass vial. The CNT-MNPs obtained can be stored in ultrapure water (1 mL) or dried at 80 °C until needed. To confirm that the CNT-MNPs composite was obtained, the synthesized material was characterized by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) [26].

2.4 Magnetic SPE procedure

An amount of 5 mg of magnetic nanocomposite was put in a vial. The material was vortexed for 1 min with 1 mL of MeCN and three times with 1 mL of ultrapure water for conditioning, as in previous works [13, 26]. The solvents were discarded after each step. A volume of 10 mL of sample was added to 5 mg of activated nanocomposite and vortexed for 30 min. An external magnet was applied at the bottom of the vial and the separation of the supernatant from the composites was achieved in less than 2 min. Then, the desorption was carried out in two steps. Firstly, 5 mL of ultrapure water, 0.2 mL of hydrochloric acid (37 %) and 1 mL of DCM were added and this mixture was vortexed for 10 min. The organic layer was collected and the aqueous phase was removed. Secondly, 5 mL of ultrapure water and 1 mL of DCM were added and vortexed again for 10 min. The organic layer was collected, combined with the previous one, and stored in a glass vial at -20 °C until it was submitted to GC-pyro-AFS.

2.5 Determination of mercury species by GC-pyro-AFS

The MMHg and inorganic mercury species were ethylated before they were injected to the GC for separation. In the case of desorption samples, the DCM phase, 5 mL of acetic-acetate buffer (0.1 M, pH 3.9), and 0.25 mL of NaBEt₄ (6%) were put in a vial. Then, the mixture was manually shaken for 5 min and centrifuged for 5 min at 600 × g. The organic layer, with the ethylated forms of mercury species, was injected into the GC-pyro-AFS system where the analytes were separated in less than 6 min. To assess the degree of adsorption in the optimization process, aqueous extracts were analyzed in the same way but adding DCM (1 mL) before the ethylation.

The organic extract obtained after ethylation was evaporated by nitrogen stream at room temperature down to 50 µL in case preconcentration is needed.

2.6 Performance parameters

The main parameters employed for the monitoring of the optimization process have been adsorption efficiency (AE), preconcentration factor (PF), enrichment factor (EF), and extraction recovery (ER).

The AE was selected for monitoring the process, and it was calculated by the following equation:

$$AE = \left(1 - \frac{c_a}{c_0}\right) \times 100$$

where c_a is the concentration of the analyte in the extracted phase after adsorption and c_0 is the initial concentration.

The PF was defined as:

$$PK = \frac{V_0}{V_f}$$

where V_0 and V_f are the initial and final volumes, respectively.

The EF was defined as:

$$EF = \frac{C_f}{C_0}$$

where c_f and c_0 are the concentration of the analyte in the extract after desorption and the initial concentration in the sample, respectively.

The ER was defined as the percentage of total amount of analyte which was desorbed.

$$ER = \frac{C_f \times V_f}{C_0 \times V_0} \times 100 = EF \times \frac{V_f}{V_0} \times 100$$

2.7 Water samples

Tap, dam and river waters have been analyzed. Tap water was sampled from our lab after allowing for 10 min to flow. Dam and river waters were obtained from Toledo province (Spain). In all cases, the sampling bottle was rinsed three times with water before it was filled up. Water samples were characterized by measuring pH, conductivity, total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS) and dissolved organic carbon (DOC). Water samples were filtered through Millipore nylon membrane filters (0.45 μm).

The filtered samples were spiked at 0.1 and 1 ng mL^{-1} of MMHg and analyzed in duplicate.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Optimization of the MSPE conditions

The target mercury species in water analysis was MMHg and some key factors that influence its extraction efficiency, including the amount and type of sorbent material, the adsorption time, and the reagents and conditions used for desorption, have been considered.

3.1.1 Adsorption

Initial tests were done with 10 mL of MMHg at 5 ng mL⁻¹, 5.0 mg of magnetic nanocomposites made up of Fe (III) combined with SWCNTs #1 and vortex to uniformly disperse the sorbent into the solution. At the end of the agitation, the magnet was placed at the bottom of the vial and after less than 2 min the solution was clear in all cases. Adsorption was determined by analyzing the free fraction of analyte present in the supernatants. The aqueous supernatant was ethylated, as described in section 2.5, and injected into the GC-pyro-AFS.

The influence of the vortex time on adsorption was investigated for 5, 15, 30 and 60 min. Although there was only little variation in adsorption, the selected time was 30 min because it provided a quantitative MMHg adsorption (AE>80%).

Different amounts (1.0, 3.0, 5.0 and 7.0 mg) of magnetic nanocomposites were evaluated for an adsorption time of 30 min. The AE for 3.0, 5.0 and 7.0 mg of (SW#1)CNT-MNP were comparable and around 80% (Figure 1a). An amount of 5.0 mg was finally selected to make sure that quantitative AE values are reached in a wide concentration range.

Finally, different types of CNT-MNPs were studied (Table 1). Thus, four magnetic nanocomposites made up of MNPs modified with SWCNTs #1, SWCNTs #2, MWCNTs and DWCNTs were used. In all cases, 5.0 mg of magnetic nanocomposite and vortex mixing for 30 min were used. Figure 1b shows that SWCNTs #1 provide the highest AE (>80%). These particular CNTs are the longest and narrowest of all tested and one reason why they interact more strongly with the analytes can be that as the CNT diameter increases, both the pyramidalization angle and p-orbital misalignment angle decrease, which decreases the chemical reactivity of the C–C-bonds [27]. In addition, SWCNTs are smaller than MWCNTs in diameter and have a higher surface area per volume unity, so high extraction efficiency could be achieved [28]. Consequently, SWCNTs #1 were selected as the most suitable.

Once the optimal conditions for a quantitative extraction of MMHg were found, the effect of inorganic mercury coexistence was studied at different concentration ratios of MMHg:Hg²⁺ (1:0, 1:10, 1:25, and 1:50). Both mercury species were quantitatively adsorbed as shown in Figure 2a.

3.1.2 Desorption

The parameters affecting desorption were studied systematically after the adsorption of 10 mL of a MMHg standard solution at 5 ng mL⁻¹ onto 5.0 mg of (SW#1)CNT-MNP.

Preliminary tests for desorption were carried out with 10 mL of reagent and vortex for 10 min. Several reagents previously demonstrated in literature as suitable for MMHg extraction and/or compatible with mercury species ethylated derivatives, such as sodium thiosulfate (0.1 M), isooctane and DCM, were tested. The extracts were ethylated (as described in section 2.5) and the recoveries were 2.3, 23 and 61%, respectively. The best results were obtained with DCM but the magnetic nanocomposites were damaged by the direct addition of this solvent. To avoid this problem, desorption and ethylation were combined in one step. Thus, 5 mL of buffer at pH 3.9, 2 mL of DCM and 0.25 mL of NaBEt₄ (6%) were added in this order and vortexed for 10 min. Under these conditions the magnetic nanocomposite was not damaged by the DCM, but the ER was around 45%. Since the addition of DCM in presence of water did not damage the nanocomposite we decided to keep this for the following experiments, even though simultaneous desorption and ethylation was not possible. Thus, firstly 5 mL of deionized water, then 2 mL of DCM and finally 0.2 mL of hydrochloric acid were added and the mixture was vortexed for 10 min. The use of hydrochloric acid to improve the extraction of MMHg into an organic solvent was previously reported [29, 30]. This selective extraction can be related to the fact that the chloride complex formed from MMHg (MeHgCl) is more soluble in organic solvents than the one formed from inorganic Hg ([HgCl₄]²⁻). The ER obtained was around 80%. To further increase the ER, a second step was carried out with 5 mL of deionized water and 2 mL of DCM followed by vortex agitation for 10 min. The DCM extracts obtained from both steps were combined, ethylated, and injected into the chromatographic system. Under these conditions, the ER of MMHg was higher than 90%. The volume of DCM was decreased from 2 to 1 mL in each step obtaining the same recoveries.

Experiments with nanocomposites made up of SWCNTs #1, SWCNTs #2, MWCNTs and DWCNTs were conducted in the optimized conditions. The ERs of MMHg were 90% for (SW#1)CNT-MNP; 80% for (SW#2)CNT-MNP; 70% for (MW)CNT-MNP and less than

40 % for (DW)CNT-MNP. Therefore, the magnetic nanocomposite with SWCNTs #1 was selected for future experiments.

In contrast to adsorption, there was a great difference in desorption of both mercury species. Desorption was above 80% for MMHg while it was below 5% for Hg^{2+} (Figure 2b). This means that this method can be used for the selective monitoring of the most concerning mercury species, MMHg, in the presence of the major occurring species, Hg^{2+} . Therefore, it enables the combination of MSPE (procedure 2.4) and nitrogen stream evaporation of organic extract after the ethylation (procedure 2.5) which allows to achieve a preconcentration factor up to 150 for MMHg.

3.2 Reusability

Several adsorption-desorption cycles of MMHg using the same CNT-MNPs were performed to evaluate the reusability under the experimental conditions optimized above. After one desorption process, the CNT-MNPs were washed with ultrapure water (3 x 1 mL) and vortex agitation for 1 min. Then, the CNT-MNPs were dried at 95 °C for about 48 h and conditioned with MeCN and ultrapure water (see procedure 2.4) to start the process again. This last fraction of water was analysed and no peaks of mercury species were found.

The AE was close to the maximum (80-90%) in the first 3 cycles. Then, the adsorption decreased but remained around 70-75% in the following four cycles. In the eighth cycle, there was a drop in AE to 40% and the nanocomposites began to lose their magnetic properties. The desorption efficiency remained constant around 100% of the adsorbed MMHg in the eight cycles, which means that the reusing of (SW#1)CNT-MNPs did not affect the desorption of the analytes.

Therefore, it is possible to reuse these CNT-MNPs up to seven times with a little decrease of efficiency after the third reuse.

3.3 Analytical performance

The linearity was checked by injecting a set of derivatized standards in the range 1–100 ng mL^{-1} of MMHg, exhibiting a linear regression slope of $1.846(\pm 0.041)$ and determination coefficient of $R^2 = 0.997$. The intercept was found to be negligible by using the Student's t-test ($p=0.05$). The LOD and LOQ were obtained as the sample concentration that caused a peak with a height 3-fold and 10-fold the base line noise level respectively. The procedural LOD and LOQ for MMHg were 5.4 pg mL^{-1} and 17.9 pg mL^{-1} , respectively, applying additional preconcentration by nitrogen stream.

The relative standard deviations (% RSD) of the proposed method in six independent experiments with MMHg at 1 ng mL^{-1} was 5.9% for adsorption and 4.2% for desorption.

The reproducibility in terms of batch-to-batch deviations were also evaluated using three different batches of synthesized composite sorbent for the extraction of standards of MMHg at 5 ng mL^{-1} . There were no statistically differences between batches in the recoveries ($p=0.083 > 0.05$) and the RSD was lower than 10% (7.6 % RSD).

3.4 Analysis of water samples

The method was applied to the determination of MMHg in tap, dam and river waters. The main features of these samples are summarized in Table 2. The pH was between 6 and 8 and the conductivity was higher in dam and river waters than in tap water. Tap and dam waters had lower TSS than river water, whereas dam and river waters had higher TDS than tap water. DOC concentrations were similar in both tap and dam water samples while for river water sample was up to 20-fold higher.

The natural concentrations of mercury species were below the detections limits in all samples. Thus, to demonstrate the applicability of the method, the samples were spiked with MMHg at 0.1 and 1 ng mL^{-1} . Duplicate aliquots of 10 mL of each real water sample were submitted to analysis and injected by triplicate in the GC-pyro-AFS. As an example, chromatograms of dam water with and without MMHg spike are shown in Figure 3. Duplicate analyses of tap, dam, and river water samples previously spiked at 0.1 and 1 ng mL^{-1} were carried out to calculate EFs. The EFs obtained were 3.18, 3.47, and 2.89 for tap, dam, and river, respectively. The ERs obtained were quantitative regardless of the spiked MMHg concentration and the nature of the studied matrix (Table 2). Nonetheless, the ERs were lower in the river sample, in which DOC is high. This can be due to the interaction, presumably by complexation, of organic matter with MMHg, which can hinder its adsorption to the nanosorbent.

4. Conclusions

In this work, a simple, fast and reliable method for mercury speciation analysis in water samples was developed. The method is based on MSPE using MNPs modified with CNTs as sorbents and determination of mercury species by GC-pyro-AFS after derivatization by ethylation. The method benefits from a simple and fast synthesis of CNT-MNPs nanocomposites because there is no need for further modification of the surface of CNTs. It also benefits from the easy and fast separation provided by MSPE. Other remarkable advantages are the low amount of sorbent (5.0 mg) and organic solvents as well as the fact that nanocomposite can be reused up to seven times. The method is selective for MMHg preconcentration even in the presence of inorganic mercury.

However, this methodology is still far from being readily applicable to routine laboratory analysis. The main reason for this is that the supply of CNTs of the particular characteristics that make them suitable for a particular method is often discontinued by the manufacturers. Therefore, efforts should be made to fill this gap but it is still worthy to keep working on this approach because of the outstanding advantages that it provides.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (CTQ2016-78793-P) and Junta de Comunidades de Castilla–La Mancha (PEIC-2014-001-P) for supporting this work.

References

- [1] K.M. Rice, E.M. Walker, M. Wu, C. Gillette, E.R. Blough, Environmental mercury and its toxic effects, *J. Prev. Med. Public. Health.* 47 (2014) 74-83.
- [2] T. Syversen, P. Kaur, The toxicology of mercury and its compounds, *J. Trace. Elem. Med. Bio.* 26 (2012) 215-226.
- [3] C.T. Driscoll, R.P. Mason, H.M. Chan, D.J. Jacob, N. Pirrone, Mercury as a global pollutant: sources, pathways, and effects, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47 (2013) 4967-4983.
- [4] M. Amde, Y. Yin, D. Zhang, J. Liu, Methods and recent advances in speciation analysis of mercury chemical species in environmental samples: a review, *Chem. Spec. and Bioavailab.* 28 (2016) 51-65.
- [5] J.J. Berzas Nevado, R.C.R. Martín-Doimeadios, E.M. Krupp, F.J. Guzmán Bernardo, N. Rodríguez Fariñas, M. Jiménez Moreno, D. Wallace, M.J. Patiño Roperó, Comparison of gas chromatographic hyphenated techniques for mercury speciation analysis, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1218 (2011) 4545-4551.
- [6] R.M. Blanco, M.T. Villanueva, J.E.S. Uria, A. Sanz-Medel, Field sampling, preconcentration and determination of mercury species in river waters, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 419 (2000) 137-144.
- [7] K. Leopold, M. Foulkes, P. Worsfold, Methods for the determination and speciation of mercury in natural waters- a review, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 663 (2010) 127-138.
- [8] J. Huber, K. Leopold, Nanomaterial-based strategies for enhanced mercury trace analysis in environmental and drinkingwaters, *Trac-Trends. Anal. Chem.* 80 (2016) 280-292.
- [9] E.C.D. Ramalhosa, S. Río-Segade, Analytical methods for mercury speciation in several matrixes: a review, *Trends. Chromatogr.* 2 (2008) 43-77.
- [10] J. Płotka-Wasyłka, N. Szczepańska, M. de la Guardia, J. Namieśnik, Modern trends in solid phase extraction: new sorbent media, *Trac-Trends. Anal. Chem.* 77 (2016) 23-43.
- [11] A.V. Herrera-Herrera, M.Á. González-Curbelo, J. Hernández-Borges, M.Á. Rodríguez-Delgado, Carbon nanotubes applications in separation science: a review, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 734 (2012) 1-30.
- [12] J. Xu, J. Zheng, J. Tian, F. Zhu, F. Zeng, C. Su, G. Ouyang, New materials in solid-phase microextraction, *Trac-Trends. Anal. Chem.* 47 (2013) 68-83.
- [13] A.I. Corps Ricardo, F.J. Guzmán Bernardo, M. Zougagh, R.C.R. Martín-Doimeadios, Á. Rios, Magnetic nanoparticles – carbon nanotubes hybrid composites for selective solid-phase extraction of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and determination by ultra-high performance liquid chromatography, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 409 (2017) 5125-5132.
- [14] W.C. Tseng, K.C. Hsu, C.S. Shiea, Y.L. Huang, Recent trends in nanomaterial-based microanalytical systems for the speciation of trace elements: a critical review, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 884 (2015) 1-18.
- [15] M.J. Shadbad, A. Mohebbi, A. Soltani, Mercury(II) removal from aqueous solutions by adsorption on multi-walled carbon nanotubes, *Korean J. Chem. Eng.* 28 (2011) 1029-1034.
- [16] K. Yaghmaeian, R.K. Mashizi, S. Nasser, A.H. Mahvi, M. Alimohammadi, S. Nazmara, Removal of inorganic mercury from aquatic environments by multi-walled carbon nanotubes, *J. Environ. Health. Sci. Eng.* 13 (2015) 55-63.
- [17] F. Homayoon, H. Faghihian, F. Toriki, Application of a novel magnetic carbon nanotube adsorbent for removal of mercury from aqueous solutions, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 24 (2017) 11764-11778.

- [18] D. Deng, S. Zhang, H. Chen, L. Yang, H. Yin, X. Hou, C. Zheng, Torki, Online solid sampling platform using multi-wall carbon nanotube assisted matrix solid phase dispersion for mercury speciation in fish by HPLC-ICP-MS, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* 30 (2015) 882-887.
- [19] J. Muñoz, M. Gallego, M. Valcárcel, Speciation of organometallic compounds in environmental samples by gas chromatography after flow preconcentration on fullerenes and nanotubes, *Anal. Chem.* 77 (2005) 5389-5395.
- [20] C. Zhang, J. Sui, J. Li, Y. Tang, W. Cai, Efficient removal of heavy metal ions by thiol-functionalized superparamagnetic carbon nanotubes, *Chem. Eng. J.* 210 (2012) 45-52.
- [21] C. Herrero-Latorre, J. Barciela-García, S. García-Martín, R.M. Peña-Crecente, J. Otárola-Jiménez, Magnetic solid-phase extraction using carbon nanotubes as sorbents: a review, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 892 (2015) 10-26.
- [22] S. Ma, M. He, B. Chen, W. Deng, Q. Zheng, B. Hu, Magnetic solid phase extraction coupled with inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry for the speciation of mercury in environmental water and human hair samples, *Talanta.* 146 (2016) 93-99.
- [23] S. Zhang, H. Luo, Y. Zhang, X. Li, J. Liu, Q. Xu, Z. Wang, In situ rapid magnetic solid-phase extraction coupled with HPLC-ICP-MS for mercury speciation in environmental water, *Microchem. J.* 126 (2016) 25-31.
- [24] M. Jiménez Moreno, M.Á. Lominchar, M.J. Sierra, R. Millán, R.C.R. Martín-Doimeadios, Fast method for the simultaneous determination of monomethylmercury and inorganic mercury in rice and aquatic plants, *Talanta.* 176 (2018) 102–107.
- [25] G. Morales-Cid, A. Fekete, B.M. Simonet, R. Lehmann, S. Cárdenas, X. Zhang, M. Valcárcel, P. Schmitt-Kopplin, In situ synthesis of magnetic multiwalled carbon nanotube composites for the clean-up of (Fluoro)Quinolones from human plasma prior to ultrahigh pressure liquid chromatography analysis, *Anal. Chem.* 82 (2010) 2743-2752.
- [26] V. Moreno, M. Zougagh, Á. Ríos, Hybrid nanoparticles based on magnetic multiwalled carbon nanotube-nanoC₁₈SiO₂ composites for solid phase extraction of mycotoxins prior to their determination by LC-MS, *Microchim. Acta.* 183 (2016) 871-880.
- [27] S. Banerjee, S.S. Wong, Demonstration of diameter-selective reactivity in the sidewall ozonation of SWNTs by resonance raman spectroscopy, *Nano. Lett.* 4 (2004) 1445-1450.
- [28] C. Herrero Latorre, J. Álvarez Méndez, J. Barciela García, S. García Martín, R.M. Peña Crecente, Carbon nanotubes as solid-phase extraction sorbents prior to atomic spectrometric determination of metal species: A review, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 749 (2012) 16-35.
- [29] R.C.R. Martín-Doimeadios, M. Monperrus, E. Krupp, D. Amouroux, O.F.X. Donard, Using speciated isotope dilution with GC-inductively coupled plasma MS to determine and unravel the artificial formation of monomethylmercury in certified reference sediments, *Anal. Chem.* 75 (2003) 3202-3211.
- [30] J.J. Berzas Nevado, R.C.R. Martín-Doimeadios, F.J. Guzmán Bernardo, M. Jiménez Moreno, Determination of monomethylmercury in low- and high-polluted sediments by microwave extraction and gas chromatography with atomic fluorescence detection, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 608 (2008) 30-37.

Table 1. Main characteristics and manufacturer of CNTs used in this work.

Type of CNTs	Manufacturer	Length (μm)	Diameter (nm)
SWCNTs#1	Sigma-Aldrich	10-30	0.9-1.2
SWCNTs#2	Sigma-Aldrich	2-5	1.2-1.5
DWCNTs	XinNano Materials	2-6	1-3
MWCNTs	Nano-Lab	5-20	30 \pm 15

(SW: single-walled; DW: double-walled; MW: multi-walled; CNTs: carbon nanotubes)

Table 2. Physicochemical characteristics of water samples (mean \pm standard deviation, n=3) and extraction recoveries (ER) of spiked MMHg (mean \pm standard deviation, n=6).

Sample	pH	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	TSS (mg L^{-1})	TDS (mg L^{-1})	DOC (mg L^{-1})	ER (%) at 0.1 ng mL^{-1}	ER (%) at 1 ng mL^{-1}
Tap water	6.58 \pm 0.05	227.0 \pm 1.0	0.83 \pm 0.58	95.3 \pm 2.1	6.49 \pm 0.91	93.6 \pm 4.7	96.3 \pm 1.3
Dam water	8.25 \pm 0.05	1588 \pm 19	2.0 \pm 1.0	563.3 \pm 6.4	6.7 \pm 1.7	91.4 \pm 6.1	97.2 \pm 1.3
River water	7.27 \pm 0.01	1470.7 \pm 7.1	27.3 \pm 1.7	686.7 \pm 5.3	126 \pm 20	79 \pm 15	86 \pm 11

Figure 1. Effect of the amount of nanocomposite (a) and type of CNT-MNPs (b) on the adsorption of MMHg.

Figure 2. Effects of different concentration of Hg^{2+} , keeping constant concentration of MMHg at 1 ng mL^{-1} on adsorption (a) and desorption (b) of mercury species.

a)

b)

2+

Figure 3. Chromatograms of standard 1 (1 ng mL⁻¹ of MMHg and 10 ng mL⁻¹ of Hg²⁺), standard 2 (5 ng mL⁻¹ of MMHg and 25 ng mL⁻¹ of Hg²⁺), a spiked dam water sample (1 ng mL⁻¹ of MMHg) and a non-spiked dam water sample.

